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Tuning the mechanical properties of starch-based cryogels with the aid of additives

Ruihao Zhu, Maarten A.I. Schutyser, Remko M. Boom, Lu Zhang*

Laboratory of Food Process Engineering, Wageningen University and Research, P.O. Box 17, 6700 AA Wageningen, the Netherlands

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ABSTRACT

Starch cryogel is a strong, yet light and porous material with various applications. Neat starch cryogel often suffers from suboptimal mechanical properties. In this study, we investigate the effects of additives on the material properties of starch-based cryogels. Cellulose fibre and glycerol were selected as reinforcing agent and plasticizer, respectively, to formulate starch-based hydrogels, which were freeze-dried into cryogels. Cryogels were characterized in terms of moisture content, density, microstructure, and mechanical properties. Our results show that adding cellulose fibres improves the Young's modulus and structural stability of composite materials. Conversely, adding glycerol significantly enhanced the ductility of the composite materials (i.e., higher maximum flexural strain) without compromising on their Young's modulus. We attributed these results to the impact of the additives on ice formation in the hydrogels during freezing and the structural stability of the matrix during freeze drying, which yielded in distinct microstructures of glycerol-containing samples. This study shows edible composite materials with a large range of material properties can be obtained with the aid of additives, to substitute engineering materials with equivalent properties for various applications.

1. Introduction

Foods traditionally are prepared with attractiveness for consumption, palatability, and digestibility in mind. However, some food materials have mechanical properties that are similar to those of non-edible engineering materials. Thus, one could make dual use of food materials, to construct devices or systems which are both biodegradable and completely biocompatible, and even nutritious when they are consumed at the end of their mechanical tasks. An example of such devices are robots. The concept of 'edible robots' has recently been introduced by Shintake, Sonar, Piskarev, Paik and Floreano (2017), in which an edible soft pneumatic actuator is made from a gelatin-based material instead of silicon elastomer. The philosophy behind edible robots is to create a new generation of robots that can safely interact with biological systems and open up possibilities for applications in disposable robots for exploration and digestible robots for medical purposes in human and animals.

Several recent studies have shown edible robots and robotic components made of food materials that are capable of providing energy and nutrients to the human body and can be used in combination with drug active components (Hafezi et al., 2015; Kwak, Shintake, Zhang & Floreano, 2022; Miyashita et al., 2016). Nevertheless, most research on

edible robots typically only explores the integration of existing edible materials into robots, without assessing the optimal choice of the material, its formulation and processing conditions to reach certain material property requirements. Besides, the properties of food materials have drawbacks such as low stiffness and high density, which limit their applications as structural components for robot bodies. To enable food materials to replace conventional light weight polymer materials in robotic applications, such as expanded polypropylene (EPP) foam, it is therefore of interest to study how one can systematically adapt the mechanical properties of food materials into high stiffness and low density.

Starch is an abundant biopolymer, which is inexpensive, completely digestible and has a high energy density of around 17 kJ per gram (Tontisirin, MacLean, Warwick, Food & Nations, 2003). There has been extensive research on starch for various applications as structural materials in packaging (Niranjana Prabhu & Prashantha, 2018), tissue engineering (Wen et al., 2020) and electronics (Xiang et al., 2022). These studies show the versatility of starch-based materials for structural engineering purposes. Depending on the applications, the mechanical properties of starch-based materials can be adapted by processing. For example, freeze dried starch cryogel is a porous and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: lu1.zhang@wur.nl (L. Zhang).

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light, yet stronger material (Baudron, Gurikov, Smirnova & Whitehouse, 2019). To adapt the mechanical properties of starch cryogels, one can make use of the physical properties of composite materials. Specifically, reducing the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composite by plasticizers (e.g., glycerol, water, and small sugars) results in a ductile material (Alonso-González, Felix, Guerrero & Romero, 2021). Conversely, filling the composite matrix with strong, rigid fibre-like particles, such as cellulose fibre, results in a reinforced composite material with enhanced mechanical strength (Nasri-Nasrabadi et al., 2014).

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the tuneable mechanical properties of starch-based cryogels with the aid of additives. Glycerol and cellulose fibre were selected as a plasticizer and a reinforcing filler, respectively, to modulate the mechanical properties of the cryogels. To obtain the final structural materials, starch/additive/water mixtures were first heated to induce the gelatinization of starch, and subsequently freeze-dried to obtain a highly porous solid material. The influence of additives on the mechanical properties (i.e., Young's modulus, maximum flexural strain) and the microstructure of the obtained starch cryogels was investigated by using texture analysis (i.e., compression test and three-point bending test) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), respectively. By comparing with other engineering materials, the results of the current work provide insights into the design of starch-based structural materials for various food applications, including edible robots.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Potato starch (80 % amylopectin and 20 % amylose, Sigma S-9765), cellulose fibre (CF, medium size, from softwood tree pulp, Sigma C6288), and micro-crystalline cellulose (MCC, from cotton linters, Sigma 310697) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich®. Glycerol (bidistilled 99.5 %) was purchased from VWR Chemicals BDH®. Demineralized water was used in all experiments. The average particle sizes (D [4,3]) of CF and MCC are 51.1 μm and 19.8 μm , respectively, measured by a particle size analyser (Mastersizer 3000, Malvern, United Kingdom). The moisture contents of the potato starch, CF, and MCC were determined by an infrared moisture analyser (Sartorius®, Germany) and were found 13.49 w/w%, 3.36 w/w% and 3.75 w/w%, respectively.

2.2. Fabrication of starch-based cryogels

2.2.1. Preparation of starch-based hydrogels

Starch-based hydrogels were prepared by mixing potato starch and additives with demineralized water at various solid concentrations. All powdered dry ingredients and glycerol were weighed and suspended in demineralized water. For the neat starch hydrogel, potato starch was weighed, and water was added to the dry powder to form a suspension with a total solid concentration of 6, 8, 12, 14, and 20 w/w%, respectively. For the starch-CF, starch-MCC and starch-glycerol gels with a fixed starch concentration, a gradient series of additives (i.e., CF, MCC, or glycerol) were weighed and mixed with 12 % potato starch in water, respectively. Besides, to explore the effect of starch and additive ratio on the material properties under the same total solid concentration, another set of samples was prepared with total solid content fixed at 12 w/w%, while the mass ratio of additive (i.e., CF or glycerol) and starch was varied from 4.2% ($M_{\text{additive}}: M_{\text{starch}} = 1:24$) to 50% ($M_{\text{additive}}: M_{\text{starch}} = 1:2$).

To ensure adequate mixing, the lidded bottles containing suspensions were placed on a magnetic stirrer (2mag®, Germany) set at 350 rpm and 90~95 °C for 1 hour. Subsequently, the suspensions were heated in a water bath set at 90 °C for 0.5 hour, to induce gelation. The obtained starch-based hydrogel was treated in a planetary vacuum mixer (ARV-310CE, Thinky Corporation®, United State of America) set

at 2000 rpm and 30 kPa for 2 min, to eliminate air bubbles and to ensure a homogeneous gel.

2.2.2. Preparation of starch-based cryogels

The starch-based gel was poured into a mould while still warm. Two types of moulds were used, a cylindrical shape ($\phi=20$ mm, $H=20$ mm) and a cuboid shape ($L \times W \times H = 50$ mm \times 20 mm \times 10 mm). The moulds had an open structure to allow freeze drying of the gels. The gel samples with moulds were frozen at -20 °C for 24 h and subsequently dried in a pilot freeze dryer (Christ Epsilon® 2-10D, Germany) for 72 h. The dried cryogels were stored at room condition (temperature = 22.4 °C, relative humidity = 32.0 %) in sealed bags until further analysis. The cryogels showed varying degrees of shrinkage after freeze drying. The dimensions were measured after freeze drying prior to further analysis.

2.3. Characterizations of starch-based cryogels

2.3.1. Moisture content analysis

The residual moisture content of the starch-based cryogels was determined by drying in an oven (BINDER®, Germany) set at 105 °C for 1 hour, followed by cooling in a Nalgene™ desiccator at ambient temperature for 0.5 h. This drying and cooling cycle was repeated until the samples reached a constant weight, indicated by a weight difference of less than 2 mg between two consecutive measurements. The moisture content (on wet basis) was calculated:

$$X (\%) = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

in which, X is the moisture content of samples (w/w%), m_1 is the total weight of samples before drying (g), and m_2 is the total weight of samples after drying (g).

2.3.2. Bulk density analysis

The dimensions of the cryogel were determined with a digital calliper (Mitutoyo®), from which the total volume of the sample was calculated. The bulk density of the cryogels was then calculated by dividing the total mass of the sample by its total volume:

$$\rho_{\text{cryogel}} = \frac{M_{\text{cryogel}}}{V_{\text{cryogel}}} \quad (2)$$

in which, ρ_{cryogel} is the bulk density (kg/m^3) of starch-based cryogel samples, M_{cryogel} is the total mass (kg) and V_{cryogel} is the total volume (m^3).

2.3.3. Volume fraction estimation

The volume fraction (ϕ_{v_i} , v/v%) of each solid component (i.e., starch, additives), the residual water ($\phi_{v_{\text{water}}}$, v/v%) and the air ($\phi_{v_{\text{air}}}$, v/v%) in the cryogel samples were estimated by the below functions:

$$\phi_{v_i} = \frac{m_i}{\rho_i \cdot V_{\text{cryogel}}} \times 100\%, \text{ for } i = \text{starch, CF, MCC, glycerol} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_{v_{\text{water}}} = \frac{M_{\text{cryogel}} \cdot X}{\rho_{\text{water}} \cdot V_{\text{cryogel}}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_{v_{\text{air}}} = 100 - \sum \phi_{v_i} - \phi_{v_{\text{water}}}, \text{ for } i = \text{starch, CF, MCC, glycerol} \quad (5)$$

in which, the density of starch, cellulose (CF/MCC), glycerol (ρ_i , $i=\text{starch, CF/MCC, glycerol}$) and water were taken from literature as 1500 kg/m^3 (Jane, 2009), 1580 kg/m^3 (Sun, 2005), 1260 kg/m^3 , and 1000 kg/m^3 , respectively. The Eqs. (3), (4), and (5) given above are under the assumption that the mixture is homogenous and ideal, so there is no volume change during the mixing process. It is noted that glycerol was considered here as a 'solid' component for the calculation of its volume fraction.

2.3.4. Mechanical properties and microstructural analyses of cryogels

Two types of texture analysis were performed on the starch-based cryogels, namely a single compression test and a three-point bending test, using an Instron® texture analyser. Two representative mechanical properties for structural materials, i.e., Young's modulus (E , MPa) and maximum flexural strain (ε_{max} , %) were calculated based on the force-displacement data, representing the strength and the flexibility of the material, respectively. These two parameters were selected due to their importance in designing aerofoils, as shown in a previous work on the development of edible drone (Kwak et al., 2022).

For the compression test, the cylindrical cryogel sample was compressed with a constant displacement speed of 15 mm/min. The test was terminated when a 30 % drop from the peak force (N) was reached. For the three-point bending test, a flexure fixture was used to press on the cuboidal cryogel sample at a constant displacement speed of 10 mm/min. The distance between the two outer supports was 30 mm. The test was terminated when an 80 % drop from the peak force (N) was reached, indicating the sample was broken. From both tests, force-displacement data was obtained for calculating Young's modulus and maximum flexural strain. Young's modulus (E , MPa) of the sample was calculated (Askeland & Fulay, 2005):

$$E = \frac{\Delta FH}{\Delta d \pi r^2} \quad (6)$$

in which, E is the Young's modulus (MPa), ΔF is the force loading difference on the samples (N) taken from the linear part of the force-displacement curve, Δd is the relative displacement (mm), H (mm) and r (mm) are the original height and radius of the cylindrical cryogel sample, respectively.

The maximum flexural strain (%) can be calculated using the results from the three-point bending test. It was calculated (Standard & ISO, 1998):

$$\varepsilon_{max} = \frac{6Dd_{max}}{L^2} \quad (7)$$

in which, d_{max} is the displacement (mm) at the breakage of samples. D is the thickness (mm) of the cuboidal cryogel sample, and L is the length (mm) of the support span.

The microscopic images of the starch-based cryogels were taken by using a JEOL® JCM-7000 Tabletop scanning electron microscope (SEM). The cryogel sample was sliced into pieces with 1 mm thickness using a blade and sputter coated with gold in plasma for 2 min to obtain a 10 nm thick coating before SEM analysis. The average pores area was calculated with the software ImageJ 1.52.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Three batches of independent hydrogel preparation and freeze drying experiments were conducted to obtain cryogels. For the mechanical properties test, four cryogel samples of each formulation were measured from each batch of samples. Data analysis was performed using MATLAB R2021b and graphs were made using Origin 2022b, OriginLab Corporation, USA. The error bars in the charts indicate the standard error of each formulation ($n = 12$). Statistical significance analysis was performed using IBM SPSS statistics using Tukey's-b method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effects of additives on freeze drying of cryogels

3.1.1. Residual moisture content in cryogels

The residual moisture content in the cryogel samples was determined to investigate the influence of the formulation on the freeze drying process (see Fig. 1).

For neat starch samples, increasing the total solid concentration did not affect the residual moisture content, which was around 10.5% (see Fig. 1a). For materials with fixed starch concentration (i.e., varied total solid concentration), increasing the cellulose fibre (CF) or microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) concentrations in the hydrogels slightly affected the residual moisture content in the cryogels. However, no obvious trend can be observed. Interestingly, when the total solid concentration was fixed at 12 w/w% in the hydrogels, increasing the percentage of CF concentration resulted in cryogels with reduced moisture content (see Fig. 1b). A more obvious decreasing trend of residual moisture content was observed here. This might be because that insoluble CF particles replaced part of the starch in the matrix, which acted as nucleating agents promoting ice crystal formation (Hou et al., 2021). The changes in the ice crystal formation affected the residual moisture content after freeze drying as well as the final microstructure of the cryogel (see Section 3.1.3).

In contrast, increasing the glycerol concentration from 0.5 w/w% to 6 w/w% drastically increased the residual moisture content in the cryogels (see Fig. 1a). This was even more evident when the total mass of starch and glycerol was fixed at 12 w/w% (see Fig. 1b). This is expected because glycerol, having a low molecular weight and three hydroxyl groups, is often used as a cryoprotectant to reduce the freezing point of water (Pop et al., 2015). During the freezing process, the matrix surrounding the ice crystals become quite concentrated in glycerol, which can lead to very strong freezing point depression. The end result is that a significant fraction of water remains unfrozen, and cannot be removed at a later stage due to the low activity of the remaining water in the

Fig. 1. (a) residual water content (wt%) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the total solid concentration (w/w%) in the hydrogels: starch concentration was fixed at 12 w/w% for samples with additives (i.e., CF, MCC or glycerol); (b) residual water content (wt%) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the mass ratio of additive (i.e., CF or glycerol) and starch (%) in the hydrogels: the total solid concentration of substrates (starch with or without additive) was fixed at 12 w/w%. Dashed lines are drawn to guide the eye.

presence of the glycerol (Dashnau, Nucci, Sharp & Vanderkooi, 2006). Both the residual water and the plasticizing effect (lower T_g) of glycerol will influence the physical stability of the matrix during drying, and eventually the final structure of the cryogel. Indeed, the freeze-dried materials containing glycerol exhibited more shrinkage and collapse than the other samples without glycerol, which was also evident when comparing the bulk density of the samples. We expect the differences in the residual moisture content of the cryogel samples will affect their mechanical properties, which will be discussed later.

3.1.2. Bulk density

For materials to be used as structural components, one important property is their bulk density. When the volume of a structure is constant, it is obvious that an increase in the solids mass results in a higher density. Previous research showed that increasing the starch concentration resulted in higher densities and smaller pore size of starch cryogels (Zou & Budtova, 2021). This was also observed in our experiments (see Fig. 2), where a linear increase in bulk density was observed with increasing total solids concentration. Specifically, when we varied the solids concentration in the hydrogels between 12~18 w/w%, we were able to obtain cryogel samples with a final bulk density ranging from 150 kg/m³ to 200 kg/m³. These values are comparable to the bulk density of engineering materials (e.g., expanded polypropylene) used for building model aircrafts.

However, increasing the glycerol concentration in the hydrogels led to a nonlinear increase in the bulk density of the cryogels. When the glycerol concentration was increased to 6 w/w%, the final bulk density of cryogel was found to be around 360 kg/m³, which was significantly higher than all other samples. As discussed previously, this formulation also resulted in a much higher residual moisture content and severe shrinkage/collapsing of the matrix after drying. The matrix had an overall lower T_g due to the plasticizing effect of glycerol, which collapsed during drying process. The reduction of volume and increase of mass yielded in an overall increased bulk density of starch cryogel samples with glycerol.

3.1.3. Volume fraction of components

Starch hydrogel is transformed into a lightweight foam-like structure by the freeze drying process, which is essentially the replacement of ice crystals by air voids. The structure can also be regarded as the even distribution of solids (such as starch and cellulose) within a space of fixed volume formed by a hydrogel. During the fabrication of starch-based cryogels in the current work, the hydrogel samples were placed in a mould with a fixed volume. A consistent shrinkage was observed for samples containing neat starch as well as samples containing cellulose particles as additives (CF and MCC), despite the different formulations used. For the samples containing glycerol, more shrinkage was observed when the glycerol concentration in the hydrogels was set high. Similar results were reported by de Graaf, Karman and Janssen (2003) that obvious shrinkage of the starch-based bar was observed after drying when the glycerol contents were more than 15 w/w% in total solids.

The results of the final volume and residual moisture content of the cryogels were used to estimate the volume fractions of each component (i.e., air, residual water, starch, and additives). The changes in volume fractions of solid components are thought to be strongly linked to the mechanical properties (i.e., stiffness and ductility) of the cryogels (see Fig. 2). For the neat starch samples, increasing starch concentrations resulted in cryogels with a higher density, i.e., higher mass when the volume was similar. The volume fraction of starch increased as well as the volume fraction of the residual water (see Fig. 2). The volume fraction of air, essentially the porosity of the sample, decreased. Hence, a denser structure was obtained with increased starch concentration, which is consistent with literature data (Baudron et al., 2019). For cryogel samples containing the two types of cellulose particles, the results of estimated volume fractions of each component were very similar. Because the volume fraction occupied by solid components (i.e., starch network and cellulose particles) increased, it is expected that the materials will become stiffer. Although CF and MCC had different particle sizes, we did not observe significant changes on the structure of the cryogels containing these additives. It could be interesting to further study the effects of insoluble cellulose particles with different sizes (i.e.,

Fig. 2. Volume fractions (v/v%) of each component (i.e., air, residual water, additive, and starch) and bulk density (kg/m³) of the starch-based cryogels as influenced by the total solid concentration (w/w%) of the hydrogels: (a) neat starch; (b) starch + CF; (c) starch + MCC; and (d) starch + glycerol.

from nano- to micro-millimetres) on the properties of cryogels. However, this is out of the scope of the current work. Furthermore, for samples containing glycerol, the volume fraction of plasticizing components (i.e., water and glycerol) were significantly higher than other samples. This is expected to reduce the stiffness of the cryogels, making the structure more deformable.

3.1.4. Microstructure of cryogels

During freeze-drying of starch-based hydrogels, solid ice was sublimated which resulted in small pores in the cryogel matrix. Thus, the final microstructure of the cryogel is strongly linked to the morphology of solid ice and the deformability of the composite matrix. To investigate the effects of additives on the microstructure of cryogels, scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of selected samples were taken (see Fig. 3). The average pores area can be found in Appendix Table A.1.

For neat starch samples, increasing starch concentration resulted in a denser structure with smaller pores (see Fig. 3), which is consistent with previous research on this topic (Zou & Budtova, 2021). Comparing neat starch samples and CF-containing samples with the same total solid concentrations, the pore size of neat starch cryogels was slightly smaller (see Fig. 3). Moreover, compared with neat starch cryogels, the microstructure of glycerol-containing cryogels showed larger pores, inhomogeneous pore size distribution and thicker cell walls (see Fig. 3). This can be linked to the results shown in Fig. 2, showing the comparison of pure starch, CF-modified and glycerol-modified starch cryogel.

The pore size of neat starch cryogel with the same dry matter was smaller than that of cellulosic reinforced starch cryogels. The main reason is that pure materials own higher compatibility than mixed materials, and presence of another compound interferes with the formation of a homogeneous structure. During the gelatinization of a pure starch-based solution, water molecules equally access the starch granules, leading to swelling. Upon break down of starch granules, a more homogenous network is formed (Jenkins & Donald, 1998). After freezing and freeze-drying, the ice crystals are sublimated, and small-size pores can be observed. When adding fibres into the system, the competition

between water and fibres affects the swelling behaviour of starch, especially close to the fibre. Besides, the compactness of the network is related to the contents of starch, more starch molecules lead to more denser network ramifications during retrogradation. Hence, the assembling network is formed, and the pores of starch cryogel are smaller (Zou & Budtova, 2021).

As explained in Fig. 2, the group of samples with the addition of glycerol exhibited a non-linear relationship when the amount of solid matter content exceeded 14 g / 100 g (glycerol content in total solid mass is 16.7 wt.%). This point coincides with the visual shrinkage of the starch cryogel sample after the freeze-drying process, as Fig. 3 shows. Similar results were reported by de Graaf et al. (2003) that the obvious shrinkage of the starch-based bar was observed when the glycerol contents were more than 15 wt%. Plasticization effect mentioned by Özeren, Olsson, Nilsson and Hedenqvist (2020) proves that with a reduced T_g of the composited material, the internal structure of glycerol-containing cryogels collapsed more easily during sublimation of solid ice due to capillary forces. This is in line with our observation that starch cryogels containing a high amount of glycerol showed more shrinkage after freeze drying. Although the pores became larger in the samples containing a high amount of glycerol, the overall volume fraction of air (porosity) of the cryogel was smaller (see Fig. 2). Therefore, larger pores observed in the microstructure does not necessarily mean the material will be less stiff. These changes in the microstructure of cryogels discussed above are expected to influence their mechanical properties.

3.2. Effect of additives on mechanical properties of cryogels

3.2.1. Young's modulus

The effect of hydrogel formulation on two representative mechanical properties of cryogels, namely Young's modulus (stiffness) and maximum flexural strain (ductility), was investigated. From the results of the single compression test, the Young's modulus of the cryogels was determined (see Fig. 4). For neat starch samples, a higher starch

Fig. 3. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of starch-based cryogels obtained after freeze-drying of hydrogels with different solid concentration of starch and additives: (a) neat starch, 12 w/w%; (b) starch 8 w/w% + CF 4 w/w%; (c) starch 8 w/w% + glycerol 4 w/w%; (d) neat starch, 16 w/w%; (e) starch 12 w/w% + CF 4 w/w%; (f) starch 12 w/w% + glycerol 4 w/w%; (g) neat starch, 18 w/w%; (h) starch 12 w/w% + CF 6 w/w%; (i) starch 12 w/w% + glycerol 6 w/w%. Neat starch samples with concentrations of 16 w/w% and 18 w/w% were prepared separately from previous batches for SEM imaging.

Fig. 4. (a) Young's modulus (MPa) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the total solid concentration in the hydrogels: starch concentration was fixed at 12 w/w % for samples with additives (i.e., CF, MCC or glycerol); (b) Young's modulus (MPa) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the mass ratio of additive (i.e., CF or glycerol) and starch (%) in the hydrogels: the total solid concentration of substrates (starch with or without additive) was fixed at 12 w/w%. Results of the statistical analysis can be found in Appendix Tables A.2 and A.3. Dashed lines are drawn to guide the eye.

concentration led to a significant increase of the Young's modulus (see Fig. 4), based on statistical analysis with Tukey's-b method (see Appendix Table A.2). Although the cryogels became stiffer with increased starch concentration, they also became more brittle and were prone to breakage during the compression test (not shown in the figure). For samples with fixed starch concentration, increasing CF/MCC concentrations resulted in similar increased Young's modulus. During the compression test, starch-cellulose cryogels were not as brittle as neat starch cryogels, as no fracture occurred. Based on the results of (Darvell, 2018), starch-cellulose cryogels own stronger resistance to compression, and the further fracture of the cryogels only occurs in horizontal directions. This means the starch-cellulose fibre and starch-microcrystalline cellulose cryogels have higher stiffness and ductility than neat starch cryogels.

Interestingly, although no data points were measured for 16 w/w% and 18 w/w% neat starch samples, it seems the Young's modulus of neat starch cryogels was somewhat higher than that of the CF/MCC containing samples if the same increasing trend of Young's modulus was true (see Fig. 4, total solid concentration > 14 w/w%). This might be caused by the higher residual water content (i.e., thus the higher volume fraction of water) in CF/MCC containing samples (Figs. 1a and 2b & 2c).

Moreover, it is expected that adding glycerol will decrease the Young's modulus of the starch-based cryogels due to the plasticization effect (Alves, Mali, Beléia & Grossmann, 2007). However, our results showed that increasing the glycerol concentration in the hydrogels led to more shrinkage of the cryogels after freeze drying, which is in line with (Dhua & Mishra, 2023). Because of the trade off between decreased volume of those samples and the plasticization effect of glycerol, the effect of adding more glycerol on the Young's modulus was not significant (see Fig. 4 and Appendix Table A.2). Interestingly, the cryogels with high glycerol content became very compressible, meaning it almost returned to its original shape once the compression force was released from the matrix, which might lead to some interesting applications of this type of materials.

Our results show that the total solid concentration of the hydrogels is one of the main influential factors that determine the bulk density of the corresponding cryogels. For structural materials such as the ones used to fabricate an edible drone wing, low density is often a requirement. From the preliminary result, the cryogel with a solid concentration of 12% can have bulk density of around 150 kg/m³. Fig. 4 shows that lowering the total solid concentration also decreased the Young's modulus. However, it is interesting to investigate whether it is possible to obtain cryogels with desired low density and desired mechanical properties (e.g., Young's modulus).

Above mentioned results suggest that increasing both starch and cellulose concentrations enhance the Young's modulus of cryogels to a

different extent. We expected that there might be a trade-off when simultaneously increasing the additive concentration and decreasing the starch concentration. Therefore, we prepared a set of cryogel samples with fixed total solid concentration of 12 w/w% while varying the mass ratio of additives and starch from 1:24 to 1:2. Because adding CF and MCC showed relatively equivalent results, we selected CF for further investigation.

In the cryogels containing CF, the cellulose particles act as a rigid filler in the continuous (gelatinized) starch matrix. Fig. 4 shows the Young's modulus of cryogels decreased from around 20 MPa to 14 MPa when the mass ratio of CF and starch increased from 1:12 to 1:2 (7.7% to 33.3%). This result suggests that replacing more starch with CF seems to not only affect its volume fraction (data not shown), but also affect the Young's modulus of the starch matrix by disrupting the crosslinking of the starch network. Also, the cellulose particles might not adhere well to the starch network due to their hydrophobic nature. As evident from the previously presented microstructure of cryogels in this research, it can also be observed that at the same solid content, substituting cellulose for starch in a higher concentration (greater than 1:12) leads to a reduction in the Young's modulus of starch cryogels. The SEM observations also indicate that a denser microstructure leads to a higher Young's modulus. The Young's modulus of the composite did not decrease linearly when more starch was replaced by the CF additive as filler (see Fig. 4b). It is noteworthy that the measured Young's modulus of cryogel prepared with a mass ratio of CF and starch of 1:12 (i.e., mass ratio of CF and total solids was 7.7%) was found the highest among all the samples. However, the standard error of the texture analysis was high, therefore it is difficult to conclude whether or not there is an optimal point.

Furthermore, Fig. 4 shows the Young's modulus of cryogels drastically decreased from around 15 MPa to 2 MPa when the mass ratio of glycerol and starch increased from 1:12 to 1:2 (7.7% to 33.3%). As discussed earlier, increasing glycerol content resulted in the volume reduction (i.e., density increase) of cryogels (see Fig. 2). The same effect was observed for the cryogels with increased mass ratio of glycerol and starch. Nevertheless, the volume reduction was insufficient in causing an increase in the Young's modulus, which might be linked to the dramatic changes in the microstructure of the cryogels (see Fig. 3) as discussed above.

The Young's modulus (E_c) of a composite can be estimated, when the composite material consists of a glassy polymer matrix with a rigid filler (e.g., starch-cellulose cryogel). For this we assume that both the polymer matrix and the filler deform to the same extent when an external force is applied. There are two ways to describe the rule of mixture for obtaining a weighted mean average for the Young's modulus, named the Voigt model (Voigt, 1889) and the Reuss model (Reuss, 1929). They are known as the upper-bound and lower-bound modulus, and are

applicable to axial and transverse loading respectively:

$$E_c = (1 - f)E_p + fE_f \quad (8)$$

$$E_c = \left(\frac{1-f}{E_p} + \frac{f}{E_f} \right)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

In these rules, the volume fraction of the filler (f) and its Young's modulus (E_p), and the volume fraction of the polymer ($1 - f$) and its Young's modulus (E_p) are used as input parameters. However, it is difficult to estimate the Young's modulus of our cryogels following these rules based on the experimental data obtained in this study. Firstly, these models assume fully solid materials without pores, while the starch-based cryogels in this work are highly porous. Secondly, as discussed previously, the starch hydrogel matrix is likely disrupted by the addition of cellulose particles, rendering these models inapplicable.

Therefore, we propose to introduce a modified Gibson-Ashby model to describe our system. With the combination of Gibson-Ashby model (Gibson, 2003) and introduction of a variable (i.e., a so-called reduction factor), this model could better describe our experimental results (see Fig. 5). The Gibson-Ashby model is more often used in material science to describe the mechanical properties of cellular structures, such as foams. It provides a relationship between material stiffness and relative density:

$$E_{foam} = C_f \left(\frac{\rho_{foam}}{\rho_c} \right)^n E_c \quad (10)$$

In which, ρ_{foam} and ρ_c are the densities of the cellular structure and its bulk material. E_{foam} and E_c are the Young's moduli of the cellular structure and its bulk material. C_f is the Gibson-Ashby constant, which is dependent on the unit cell topology and geometry and can be derived from experimental results. The power constant (n) has a value of 2, which is common for open cell foams.

Instead of using the Gibson-Ashby constant C_f , we introduce here a new parameter $(1 - f)^{R_f}$ by taking the volume fraction of cellulose and a reduction factor R_f into account. The latter is introduced to describe the interfering effect of cellulose on the starch matrix (see Eq. (11)):

$$E_{foam} = (1 - f)^{R_f} \left(\frac{\rho_{foam}}{f\rho_{cellulose} + (1-f)\rho_{starch}} \right)^n E_c \quad (11)$$

In which, f is the volume fraction of cellulose in starch-cellulose system, and R_f is the reduction factor. For the starch-cellulose system, R_f is derived from experimental results and was determined to be 2. In this model, the Young's modulus of the bulk composite material (E_c) was calculated with one of the rules of mixture (Eqs. (8) & (9)), and finally the Young's modulus of the foam was calculated by using the modified

Gibson-Ashby model (Eq. (11)).

We compared how the different approaches describe the experimental data in Fig. 5. Fig. 5 illustrates that, after incorporating the reduction factor, the modified Gibson-Ashby model aligns more closely with the experimental results. This can be particularly observed in Fig. 5b. Because cellulose has a higher Young's modulus than starch, the rules of mixture predict an increasing Young's modulus with increasing mass fraction of cellulose. However, this was not observed from the experimental data. By introducing a reduction factor, the predicted Young's modulus was slightly decreasing due to the hypothesized interference of cellulose particles in the starch gel network. When the mass ratio between cellulose and starch was further increased, the Young's modulus of the cryogels decreased which might be caused by the significant changes in their microstructures after freeze drying.

3.2.2. Maximum flexural strain

From the results of the three-point bending test, the maximum flexural strain of the cryogels was determined, which refers to the measure of a material's ability to deform under stress before it fails or breaks. Fig. 6 shows increasing the total solid concentration of neat starch cryogels decreased the maximum flexural strain of the samples. This is in line with the compression test during which a more brittle material was obtained when increasing the neat starch concentration. For cellulose-containing cryogels, adding different cellulose particles (CF/MCC) did not significantly affect the maximum flexural strain (see Fig. 6). When the total solid concentration was fixed at 12 w/w%, adding more CF particles only slightly decreased the maximum flexural strain of cryogels (see Fig. 6). However, the corresponding flexural stress increased (data not shown), indicating the material became tougher. This result indicates the cellulose particles did not form a network in the matrix but were loosely distributed in the starch matrix and only acted as inert fillers.

Fig. 6 also shows that adding glycerol increased the maximum flexural strain of starch cryogels, which is consistent with another research (Nordin, Othman, Rashid & Basha, 2020). Interestingly, adding a small amount of glycerol did not seem to affect the maximum flexural strain of the cryogels (see Fig. 6). The same phenomenon was also observed when the mass ratio of glycerol and starch increased slightly (see Fig. 6). This might be explained by the anti-plasticization effect. The typical characteristics of anti-plasticization are an increased strength/stress and a decreased strain of materials with a small amount of plasticizer under deformation as compared to their unplasticized counterparts. For our cryogels containing glycerol, there is a strong interaction between glycerol and starch polymer matrix. At low glycerol contents, this interaction resulted in more brittle composite structures (Alves et al., 2007; Lourdin, Bizot & Colonna, 1997). However, continuing to add

Fig. 5. Comparison for different approaches to calculate Young's modulus. All models are explained by Eq. (11). The modified models include a variable reduction factor in Gibson-Ashby model. (a) Young's modulus (MPa) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the total solid concentration in the hydrogels: starch concentration was fixed at 12 w/w%. (b) Young's modulus (MPa) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the mass ratio of cellulose and total solids (%) in the hydrogels: the total solid concentration of substrates (starch with cellulose) was fixed at 12 w/w%.

Fig. 6. (a) maximum flexural strain (%) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the total solid concentration in the hydrogels: starch concentration was fixed at 12 w/w% for samples with additives (i.e., CF, MCC or glycerol); (b) maximum flexural strain (%) of starch-based cryogels as influenced by the mass ratio of additive (i.e., CF or glycerol) and starch (%) in the hydrogels: the total solid concentration of substrates (starch with or without additive) was fixed at 12 w/w%. Dashed lines are drawn to guide the eye.

glycerol resulted in a typical plasticizing effect, which decreased the T_g of starch-glycerol cryogel. It is worth noting that the cryogels made with two formulations, 6 w/w% glycerol addition (see Fig. 6) and a mass ratio of glycerol and starch of 1:2 (see Fig. 6), resulted in samples that can deform without breaking during the three-point bending tests. The maximum flexural strain ($\sim 40\%$ and 60%) indicated the yield point of the samples (i.e., the corresponding flexural strain when the flexural stress reached its highest). This result showed adding glycerol led to the increase of the strain hardening range of the starch-based cryogel, allowing the material to bend without experiencing fracture.

3.2.3. Ashby plot

As mentioned earlier, it is interesting to shape edible materials into structural components for robots as these are biodegradable, biocompatible, and even nutritious. However, one challenge is to develop edible materials that have equivalent properties as conventional engineering materials, such as low density and high mechanical strength. Fig. 7 compares the Young's modulus and bulk density of selected food materials, starch cryogels from this work and a type of engineering material

often used as structural body of drone (i.e., EPP foam). Compared with regular food materials, starch-based cryogels have lower density but higher Young's modulus. The overall properties of starch-based cryogels are more similar to EPP foam. Hence, starch-based cryogels show the potential to be applied as structural materials, to replace synthetic composites such as EPP foam. Besides, our work shows the possibility to obtain a range of starch cryogels with different material properties by adjusting their formulations, thereby to select appropriate materials for different application scenarios.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the effects of additives on the physical and mechanical properties of starch-based cryogels. We found that starch-based cryogels with a range of different material properties can be obtained by adjusting the formulation of the corresponding hydrogels, which showed equivalent properties as conventional engineering materials. Composite materials with improved Young's modulus can be obtained by adding cellulose fibres as a reinforcing agent. The maximum

Fig. 7. Ashby plot of Young's modulus (MPa) and bulk density (kg/m³) of expanded polypropylene (EPP) foam (Andena, Caimmi, Leonardi, Nacucchi & De Pascalis, 2019; Rumianek, Dobosz, Nowak, Dziewit & Aromiński, 2021; Weingart, Raps, Kuhnigk, Klein & Altstädt, 2020), starch-based cryogels (this work) and some representative food materials (Table A.4, in appendix).

flexural strain of starch-cellulose composite materials was more influenced by the total concentration of the solid components than by the composition of the ingredients. In contrast, adding glycerol as a plasticizer resulted in composite materials with lower Young's modulus but higher maximum flexural strain. These starch-glycerol composite materials were able to deform under larger stress without breaking. We therefore conclude that the material properties of starch-based cryogels can be tuned with the aid of additives. Edible composite materials can be formulated and processed into structural materials which fulfil requirements in various application scenarios including edible robots.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ruihao Zhu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maarten A.I. Schutyser:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Remko M. Boom:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Lu Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Appendix A. Tables

Table A.1
The average pores area of SEM image.

Samples	Average pores area (μm^2)
a. 12 % starch	2234
b. 8 % starch + 4 % CF	1833
c. 8 % starch + 4 % glycerol	10,418
d. 16 % starch	1151
e. 12 % starch + 4 % CF	1400
f. 12 % starch + 4 % glycerol	11,851
g. 18 % starch	401
h. 12 % starch + 6 % CF	807
i. 12 % starch + 6 % glycerol	48,328

Table A.2
Significance analysis of the Young's modulus of starch-based aerogels in Fig. 4.a, with Tukey's-b method.

Recipe	Concentration ^a	Mean (MPa)	n	Grouping
Neat starch	6 %	2.75	12	a
	8 %	6.77	12	a
	10 %	9.97	12	a
	12 %	18.94	12	a
	14 %	30.19	12	b
	20 %	71.35	12	b
Starch+CF	12 %+0 %	18.94	12	a
	12 %+0.5 %	20.78	12	a
	12 %+1 %	22.13	12	a
	12 %+0.75 %	27.99	12	a
	12 %+2 %	30.98	12	a
	12 %+4 %	36.08	12	b
	12 %+6 %	38.34	12	b
Starch+MCC	12 %+0.5 %	16.16	8	a
	12 %	18.67	8	a
	12 %+0.75 %	23.76	8	a
	12 %+1 %	24.34	8	a
	12 %+2 %	29.48	8	a
	12 %+4 %	34.46	8	b
	12 %+6 %	36.35	8	b
Starch+glycerol	12 %+4 %	14.03	12	a
	12 %+6 %	14.04	12	a
	12 %+2 %	14.24	12	a
	12 %+0.5 %	16.36	12	a
	12 %+1 %	17.05	12	a
	12 %+0.75 %	17.18	12	a
	12 %	18.94	12	a

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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^a Concentration refers to the solid concentration of substrates in hydrogels.

Table A.3

Significance analysis of the Young's modulus of starch-based aerogels in Fig. 4.b, with Tukey's-s-b method.

Recipe	Mass ratio ^a	Mean (MPa)	n	Grouping	
With CF	33.33 %	15.76	12	a	
	25.00 %	17.77	12	a	b
	14.29 %	18.92	12	a	b
	0.00 %	18.94	12	a	b
	5.26 %	20.23	12	a	b
	4.00 %	21.50	12	a	b
	7.69 %	24.07	12		b
With glycerol	33.33 %	1.32	12	a	
	25.00 %	4.70	12	a	b
	14.29 %	8.52	12		b
	7.69 %	14.71	12		
	5.26 %	15.17	12		c
	4.00 %	15.74	12		c
	0.00 %	18.94	12		c

^a The total solid concentration of substrates (starch with or without additive) was fixed at 12 w/w%. Mass ratio refers to the ratio between additives and total solid concentrations.

Table A.4

Young's modulus and density of selected representative food materials.

Food material	Density (kg/m ³)	Young's modulus (MPa)
Apple (raw)	544–608 ^a	6–14 ^b
Apple (dry)	240 ^a	0.25–0.45 ^f
Banana	1070 ^a	0.8–3 ^b
Potato	540 ^a	6–14 ^b
Carrot	640 ^b	20–40 ^b
Cooked meat	560–700 ^a	0.06–0.16 ^c
Commercial biscuit	410–530 ^a	20–80 ^d
Rye	720 ^a	15.1–23.6 ^e
Oat	565–650 ^b	10.4–17.8 ^b

^a From the data of Charrondiere (Charrondiere, Haytowitz & Stadlmayr, 2012).

^b From the data of Lewis (Lewis, 1990).

^c From the data of Boots (Boots et al., 2021).

^d From the data of Saleem (Saleem, 2005).

^e From the data of Molenda (Molenda & Stasiak, 2002).

^f From the data of Marzec (Marzec, Kowalska & Pasik, 2009).

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